

SIMULATION MODEL OF ROBOT MOVEMENT ALONG A DEFINED PATH DURING PRE-FLIGHT INSPECTION OF AN A320 AIRCRAFT

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Abstract: *This paper presents a simulation of a robot's movement along a predefined path during pre-flight aircraft inspection. The objective of the study is to assess the robot's ability to accurately follow the planned trajectory. The simulation model was developed in MATLAB/Simulink, and the robot's motion was evaluated based on parameters such as position deviation, orientation angle, and linear velocity. The results demonstrate that the integration of the applied technologies enables high-precision path tracking, highlighting their potential for autonomous inspection tasks in aviation and related fields.*

Keywords: *pre-flight inspection, mobile robot, path tracking, simulation modeling.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Pre-flight inspection (Yasuda, Cappabianco, Martins, & Gripp, 2022) represents a fundamental aspect of aircraft maintenance, carried out immediately prior to each flight to ensure that the aircraft is in a safe and airworthy condition. The inspection procedure consists of four main stages. The first step involves a detailed visual examination of the aircraft's exterior, aiming to identify any damage, deformations, or other visible issues affecting the aircraft structure. The condition of control surfaces located on the wings and tail is also inspected for potential damage, dirt accumulation, or ice.

The second step entails a system check, including testing of the aircraft's essential systems such as the hydraulic and pneumatic systems. The functionality of cockpit instruments and communication devices is also verified. The third step is an inspection of the aircraft's interior, which includes checking safety equipment (seat belts, life vests), inspecting the cabin, and securing cargo. The fourth step involves reviewing and verifying the required documentation, such as the flight plan, technical data, and checklists. Pre-flight inspections are typically performed by flight crew members or qualified maintenance technicians.

Since the pre-flight inspection is carried out by humans, the human factor is an unavoidable element. Fatigue and stress can lead to decreased concentration and reduced attention, potentially resulting in oversights. Human errors in aviation can cause serious consequences, endangering the safety of passengers, crew, and cargo. Additionally, such errors can lead to substantial financial costs due to physical damage to the aircraft.

The application of modern technologies helps reduce the probability of errors and increases safety levels. Automation aims to simplify the performance of specific tasks for personnel, enhancing accuracy and precision. The use of robots can further improve precision and reliability through automation processes. A robot can perform a pre-flight inspection of an aircraft. The basic concept involves a robot moving along a predefined path around the aircraft, capturing images and videos of critical points on the aircraft's fuselage. These critical points include various sensors, pitot-static system openings, control surfaces, and more. The captain, first officer, and maintenance engineers would be able to monitor the photos and videos taken by the robot via a display screen. Software installation would enable automatic recognition and detection of any changes on the aircraft's fuselage. All images and videos would be stored within the software's memory, making them readily accessible at any time.

This paper presents a simulation of a robot's movement along a predefined path during the pre-flight inspection of an Airbus A320-200 aircraft. The purpose of the simulation is to ensure precise tracking of the robot's predefined path. To address the problem of robot path-following, the programs Matlab and Simulink were used.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Mobile robots are advanced autonomous systems equipped with servo motors and sensors, capable of operating in various environments. One of the primary challenges they face is avoiding collisions with obstacles in the workspace. This issue is addressed through various navigation methods, including wheel rotation measurements, accelerometers, gyroscopes, electromagnetic beacons, and optical or magnetic signal tracking. Also, the robot is equipped with software based on the Robot Operating System (ROS), which enables remote control, navigation along a predefined path, and fully autonomous operation. Automating the pre-flight inspection process with robotic systems significantly reduces the need for human intervention and accelerates the inspection procedure. The robot is outfitted with various damage detection sensors and high-resolution cameras to ensure precise analysis of the aircraft's surface. Additionally, it incorporates autonomous navigation technologies that allow it to move around the aircraft and inspect all critical areas.

The data collected during the inspection is analyzed to detect potential issues, enabling prompt decision-making and timely execution of necessary repairs. The algorithm used to simulate the robot's movement along a predefined path consists of several key steps. The objective of the simulation is to ensure accurate tracking of the robot's designated path. The robot is equipped with a range of sensors and guidance systems, along with cameras that scan the aircraft's surface and detect potential anomalies.

Differential drive is the most common motion system in mobile robotics. It is commonly applied in robots with two wheels mounted on a shared rotating axis, each driven by its own servomotor (Figure 1). The identical methodology remains applicable to four-wheeled robotic platforms. Kinematic model for a moving robot following a path that moves with constant velocity is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}(t) \\ \dot{y}(t) \\ \dot{\varphi}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v \cdot \cos\varphi(t) \\ v \cdot \sin\varphi(t) \\ \omega(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where φ is the steering direction (rotation angle), ω is angular velocity and v is constant linear velocity (Crenganis, Biris, & Girjob, 2021). We assume that the robot is rotating in place, with its wheels spinning in opposite directions at equal speeds. As a result, the instantaneous center of rotation (ICR) lies at the midpoint between the two wheels. The angular velocity (ω) of the robot is determined by the wheel speeds and the distance between the wheels.

Figure 1: Moving robot with a differential drive

In the simulation model robot uses a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) (Ang, Chong, & Li, 2005) controller for control of rotation angle and a Pure Pursuit controller for trajectory tracking. Block diagram of PID controller is given on Figure 2.

Figure 2: Block diagram of PID controller

The reference heading angle φ_{ref} indicates the direction toward the next waypoint in the robot's trajectory.

The Pure Pursuit controller (Macenski, Singh, Martin, & Gines, 2023) is implemented as part of the robot's control system to manage its movement along a predefined path. This controller dynamically adjusts the robot's speed and steering based on its deviation from the path and the distance to the next target point.

The simulation also involves defining the exact path of movement, including the coordinates of the key positions where the robot pauses to inspect the aircraft's fuselage and plating for possible damage. For tracking robot movement, two important sensors are: position and velocity sensors. Modern solutions for positioning (satellite, Ultra-Wideband, LiDAR etc.) and velocity sensing (encoders) provide highly accurate position (up to cm to dm-level resolution) and speed (up to cm/s-level resolution) estimation with very low noise levels. Also, latency for those sensors is low. The Airbus A320-200 model is used as a reference for the simulation. Inspection checkpoints are defined according to the aircraft maintenance manual, and based on this documentation, the robot's trajectory and corresponding coordinates as illustrated in Figure 3 were established. The aircraft is considered to be stationed at the gate at the airport. In the paper, we assume that the aircraft inspection lighting is optimal, providing sufficient intensity, appropriate diffusion, and glare control to ensure visibility of details on the aircraft.

The performance of the system is evaluated by assessing tracking accuracy, the time required to complete the inspection, and any deviations or issues encountered during movement. The analysis of simulation results enables further improvements by tuning the control system parameters based on the collected data, ultimately enhancing the robot's efficiency and precision. Simulation results are generated to present the outcomes and highlight potential areas for improvement.

Figure 3: Top-down airplane projection with path of the robot in the coordinate system

3. SIMULATION MODEL

Figure 4 illustrates the Simulink-based simulation model used for testing and analyzing the robot's path-following performance. The implemented model uses a hybrid discrete-event/continuous simulation approach.

Figure 4: Simulink-based simulation model

The input parameters include the coordinates that define the robot's movement path, with the starting point marked as 1 and an initial orientation angle of 180° . An entity generator simulates the arrival of an aircraft, and the arrived entity serves as the trigger for initiating the robot's operation. The simulation incorporates an Entity Queue block, used to model queuing behavior. The queue operates on a First-In, First-Out (FIFO) principle. An Entity Server block is implemented to simulate the processing of each entity. It receives aircraft entities, processes them, and forwards them through the system. The robot is configured to inspect one aircraft at a time. Robot movement is modeled using a state machine, a mathematical model that represents system behavior through a finite number of defined states and is shown in Figure 5. The system exists in one state at any given moment and can transition to another based on incoming signals or events. Each transition may be subject to specific conditions and can trigger actions either during the transition or while the system remains in a particular state. The inputs to the state machine are the x and y coordinates that define the robot's linear motion, the angle φ (phi) that indicates the robot's orientation toward the next target point, and the start signal, which initiates robot operation. The outputs include the current state of the robot, the value n that represents the current point of inspection, rotate and move signals which correspond to rotational and linear movements between points, and the idle signal indicating that the inspection task is complete. The rotate signal is directed to the rotation block, while the move signal is passed to the motion block to control the robot's physical movement.

Figure 5: Robot movement modeling block

The rotation block in Figure 6 receives three inputs (n , pose in, and reset) and produces one output (pose out). Here, n represents the current point, pose in is the robot's current position, and reset restarts the simulation when set to 1. The pose out represents the robot's position after the rotation has been completed. Rotation is based on the current point ($pt1$) and the next point ($pt2$), whose coordinates are retrieved from memory. Using this data, the system calculates the desired heading angle. A PID controller regulates the wheel rotation speed, enabling the robot to align correctly with the next waypoint. This control is essential since the robot steers by adjusting wheel torque. The controller minimizes the error between the current and target orientation, driving the wheels accordingly. The angular velocity is integrated to compute the new position. In this closed-loop system, pose out is fed back into the controller, ensuring continuous adjustment and accurate path tracking.

Figure 6: Rotation block

The motion block, shown in Figure 7, has the same inputs and output as the rotation block: n , pose in, reset, and pose out. It receives the current point as input, and both the current and next point coordinates are retrieved from memory. These are sent to the Pure Pursuit controller, an advanced control algorithm implemented in Simulink. The controller uses parameters such as angular velocity (ω) and linear speed (v) to steer the robot from its current to the next point. It ensures precise motion execution according to the instructions from the

state machine. When the robot returns to the starting point, an idle signal is triggered, indicating that the task is complete.

Figure 7: Motion block

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

This paper presents a simulation of a robot's movement along a predefined path during the pre-flight inspection of an aircraft. The simulation is based on the inspection trajectory around an Airbus A320, illustrated in Figure 2. Table 1 presents the input parameters of the applied model. Some of the input parameters are taken from the website (AGAR, n.d.). Distance tolerance refers to the maximum permissible deviation from the actual position of a point along the predefined path. Angle tolerance defines the acceptable angular deviation when rotating towards the next point. Lookahead distance indicates how far ahead the robot "looks" along the path in order to determine the appropriate control command.

Table 1: Input parameters

Parameter group	Parameter name	Value
Path, starting position and orientation	Initial angle (°)	180
	Distance tolerance (m)	0.05
	Angle tolerance (°)	0.1
Robot parameters	Linear velocity (m/s)	1.8
	Distance between center of wheels (m)	1.219
	Scanning time (s)	2
Pure pursuit controller	Lookahead distance(m)	0.5
PID controller	P gain (K_p)	10
	I gain (K_i)	20
	D gain (K_d)	-0.2

Using the input parameters defined in the previous section, the robot's movement was simulated in Simulink, resulting in a trajectory consisting of 18 waypoints. Since the robot rotates in place to orient itself toward the next waypoint, its deviation from the linear path remains minimal. The robot's arrival at a waypoint is determined by the maximal Euclidean distance from the waypoint. The complete path followed by the robot is visualized in the first graph, shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 shows the robot's motion dynamics. Graph a) presents the linear velocity along the x and y axes, while graph b) illustrates changes in orientation angle as the robot follows the predefined path. Since we are simulating inspection process for only one aircraft simulation execution time and time for inspection is same with value of 120.6 s.

Figure 8: Simulated robot trajectory

Figure 9: Simulated robot a) position (x, y), and b) rotation angle (φ)

This simulation not only demonstrates the robot's ability to follow a precise path but also allows for the evaluation of its performance in terms of path accuracy, efficiency, and the time required to complete the inspection. The results indicate that the robot can effectively navigate the defined trajectory, ensuring thorough, timely, and efficient pre-flight inspections.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a simulation of autonomous robot movement along a predefined path during pre-flight aircraft inspection, using the Airbus A320 as a reference. The study highlights the crucial role of pre-flight inspections in ensuring flight safety and operational efficiency by enabling early detection of potential technical issues. The simulation demonstrated that the implemented control strategy significantly enhances path-tracking precision and reduces inspection time. These improvements directly contribute to increased safety and reduced operational costs. Each aircraft type follows a predefined sequence of visual inspection points, determined by its specific design and equipment. These points can be appropriate coordinates, enabling accurate camera positioning by the robotic system, whose camera can also rotate to capture various angles of the aircraft. While comparative data are currently lacking, using traditional manual inspections—which typically take between 15 and 30 minutes—as a benchmark would help validate this approach. Beyond time savings, automation ensures procedural consistency, enables defect detection, and allows systematic data recording. To further improve system performance, future work should focus on fine-tuning control parameters and integrating advanced control methods such as Model Predictive Control (MPC) or adaptive algorithms. Enhancing sensor accuracy and update frequency, applying sensor fusion techniques, and using advanced path-planning algorithms can further improve accuracy and efficiency. Additionally, real-time speed adjustment based on environmental complexity may reduce task duration. Continuous simulation and validation remain essential for iterative improvement, ensuring the robot consistently meets the demands of high-precision and time-efficient aircraft inspections.

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